

Original Research Article

Psychological Contracts and Organizational Citizenship Behavior of Teachers in Primary Schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon

Mforsoh Delia Joan Lum and Zang Ndi

Abstract

Department of Educational
Psychology, Faculty Of Education,
University of Buea, Buea, Cameroon

*Corresponding Author's E-mail:
elukongt@gmail.com

This study aimed to investigate “Psychological contracts and organizational citizenship behaviour of teachers in primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon”. The study was guided by three specific research objectives which were; to examine the influence of transactional psychological contract on organizational citizenship behavior of teachers in primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon, to investigate the effect of Relational psychological contract on organizational citizenship behavior of teachers in primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon, to ascertain the effects of Balanced psychological contract on organizational citizenship behavior of teachers in primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon. The cross sectional survey design was used and the sample was made up of 100 teachers and 15 Head Teachers who were selected from four towns in Fako Division selected through purposive or judgmental sampling techniques. The instruments used for data collection were a Likert Scale questionnaire. The data collected from teachers were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages and Pearson Product Moment correlation Coefficient to establish the relationship between psychological contracts and organizational citizenship behaviour. The findings indicated that: there was a significant and positive relationship between transactional psychological contracts and organizational citizenship behaviour ($P = 0.345$, less than 0.05). Findings equally affirmed that there was a significant and positive relationship between relational psychological contract and organizational citizenship behavior ($P = 0.021$, far less than 0.05). Finally, the findings on balanced psychological contracts revealed that there was a significant and positive relationship between balanced psychological contracts and organizational citizenship behaviour ($P = 0.130$, < 0.05). The findings indicated that psychological contracts therefore have an effect on the organizational citizenship behaviour of teachers in primary schools in Fako Division. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Head teachers should pay their teachers their due salary, what they deserve according to their workload, be fair and loyal to them, and provide them with good opportunities, like training, workshops, which will also benefit the school. Suggestions for further studies were made.

Keywords: Balanced psychological contract, Primary Schools, Psychological Contracts, Relational psychological contract, Transactional psychological contract, Organizational Citizenship Behavior

INTRODUCTION

The psychological contract concept got its origin in 1960 by Argyris (1960), which an American academician, Denise Rousseau further developed by it (Bhawna, 2019).

She later described it as the existence of the understandings, beliefs and commitments of employees with the employer. This contract basically can be seen as

a feeling of the employees which is not documented and it is very intangible in nature. The development of this contract has become an important function of human resource management in any organization. This is because it helps the employees and employers get rid of a complicated employment relationship (Sonnenberg et al., 2011). Psychological contracts also contribute a lot in developing organization. One category of employee behaviors that can be impacted by a teacher or an employee's psychological contract is organizational citizenship behavior. Organizational Citizenship Behaviors are behaviors that are not directly or explicitly recognized by a formal reward system, and promote the effectiveness of the organization. These behaviours are discretionary (Organ, 1988). There are certain demands that the school makes of the teacher that must be met if the teacher is to remain a member of the school. There are also certain minimal conditions that the teacher requires of the school and its administration. If these conditions are not met, the teacher might exhibit negative behaviours or even leave the school's employment.

Robinson and Morrison (1995) in their study on relationship between psychological contract and organizational citizenship behavior confirm that psychological contract has an effect on organizational citizenship behavior. As a result, the employees are forced to re-evaluate their psychological contract, which underlies their organizational relationship (Bellou, 2007).

Very few studies and almost none related to this topic is documented in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon. And most studies are carried out in Universities, hospitals, companies, little or none in the primary sector. Therefore, the study investigates the influence of Psychological Contract on Organizational Citizenship Behavior between staff working in different primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon.

Statement of the Problem

In every Educational Organization like in a school, employers (Administrators) and employees (teachers), are supposed to relate formally (when it comes to work), and informally (when it comes to their relationships, activities out of the formal school contract). Due to the changing employment relationship situation, a mental contract has been considered an important construct for explaining organizational citizenship behavior. However, some head teachers minimize the importance of informal contracts in schools, which causes some teachers to do their job just for the money, and not exercising their talents, that is doing extra work out of the formal contract or job which is to teach.

It has been observed that some head teachers see their teachers as mere employees, whose job is to teach and get paid, forgetting the informal aspect of it such as

trust, loyalty which is very important for the achievement of intended goals of the school. Head teachers are expected to motivate, encourage their teachers, be it verbally, relationally, transitionally, which are expected of the teachers to put in extra efforts for the realization of organizational goals. It has also been observed that most of the studies about Psychological Contract and its relationship with organizational citizenship behavior were done on Western societies, and little is known about the service sector especially in academic sector organizations (primary schools, to be specific), in Cameroon. Very few studies related to this topic are documented in the Fako Division. Therefore, the study investigates the impact of Psychological Contract on Organizational Citizenship Behavior of teachers in different academic organizations in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of psychological contract is the individual's perception of mutual obligations and expresses the mental picture of an individual obligation with counterpart obligation in a specific relationship (Rousseau, 2001). The key aspect of Rousseau's influence on the psychological contract was introducing psychological contract types. Transactional contracts involve specific monetizable exchanges, such as wages for attending work over a defined and typically short-term period of time. The focus of transactional contracts is on high wages and the absence of long-term contracts. Relational contracts involve more open-ended agreements to maintain a relationship regarding both monetized and non-monetized exchanges, such as hard work, loyalty, and job security, which are focused on development and training and a long-term career path within the firm (Rousseau, 1990). Balanced psychological contract on the other hand, combines the relational and transactional contract characteristics (Yin&Xu,2008).

From a theoretical perspective. This work made use of four theories. Theoretically, this study will make use of four theories; the two-factor theory (also known as Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory and dual-factor theory) by Frederick Herzberg (1959), Stacy Adams equity theory (1963), Vroom's Expectancy theory by Victor Vroom (1964) and Social exchange theory by George C. Homans and P. Blau (1964).

Stacey Adams theory(1993) is about the balance between the effort an employee puts into their work (input), and the result they get in return (output). Input includes hard work, skills, and enthusiasm. Output can be things like salary, recognition, and responsibility. A proper balance between input and output ensures that an employee feels satisfied and motivated, contributing to their productivity, which indicates that head teachers who are managing the schools in this study will be

Table 1. Target population, Accessible population and Sample Size

No	Schools	Accessible		Sample size	
		Head teachers	Accessible Population	Head teachers	Sample of teachers
1	GBPS Buea Town	1	8	1	5
2	CS Buea Town	1	5	1	2
3	Bambino	1	7	1	3
4	Hope Academy	1	19	1	12
5	PMS Bokwaongo	1	6	1	3
6	Helping Hand	1	8	1	5
7	PNEU Limbe	1	33	1	27
8	Defang insurance Nursery and primary school Tiko	1	8	1	3
9	Learning ladder	1	15	1	7
10	Prince of Peace	1	8	1	3
11	Kingston	1	18	1	13
12	St Joan Great Soppo	1	10	1	6
13	PIPS	1	8	1	5
14	Bokwai	1	8	1	3
15	Glorious kids Buea Town	1	8	1	3
	Total	15	169	15	100

Source: Researcher computation, 2023

encouraged to review their salary and recognition of teachers. This is to ensure that their workers (teachers) are being rewarded in proportion to their input; since these play a vital role in motivating them. This will therefore help to boost the commitment of workers since their efforts are recognized and to even do more.

From an empirical perspective, in a study carried out by Retno et al. (2021), used a sample of 313 teachers. They used quantitative methods and a sample of 313 teachers. The data collection method used was a psychological contract scale and a scale of organizational citizenship behavior. The result of this study is that there is a significant influence between the relational contract and balance contract on organizational citizenship behavior.

Bhawna (2019) used a sample of 221 employees. To test hypotheses, data was collected from 221 employees in Uttarakhand. Descriptive research design was chosen. Primary data was collected using questionnaire and survey methods. The finding statistically confirms that different components of psychological contract are having influence on organizational citizenship behavior. The result is also uniform with the several other researches on psychological contract and its relationship with OCB. The research provides valuable insights for managers to understand the employee's psychology towards various dimensions of psychological contract and how much these factors affect in strengthening the organizational citizenship behaviour of employees.

Richard Todd Oppenheim (2018) results from multiple regression suggested that each psychological contract type contributed to the variability in OCB, although only

the Relational contract type contributed to all 5 OCB categories. In addition, employer and employee fulfillment of psychological contract terms contributed to the variability in OCB, with employee fulfillment items serving as a better predictor of OCB. Employee satisfaction with work arrangement did not contribute to the variability in OCB. Additionally, contract type did not contribute to the variability in employee satisfaction with their work arrangement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study conducted in Fako division, South West Region of Cameroon, was quantitative, being descriptive and inferential in nature. It adopted the cross sectional survey research design with a target population of 117 teachers in some selected schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon. A sample size of 100 teachers for this study was arrived at using the non-probability sampling technique. This technique was used so as to directly meet with the population of interest. The distribution is as shown on Table 1

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire constructed by the researcher. A pilot test was conducted with a few copies of the questionnaires to teachers who have the same characteristics as the study area. The purpose of this was to check if there were cases of ambiguity and to know the difficulties that respondents could encounter when answering the questionnaire. Table 2

The reliability analysis report for the instrument was

Table 2. Reliability analysis report of the final instrument used for the study

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient	Variance	Number of valid cases	Number of valid items
Transactional psychological contracts	0.649	1.936	100	8
Relational psychological contracts	0.826	0.001	100	8
Balanced psychological contracts	0.742	0.000	100	8
Organizational citizenship Behaviour	0.736	0.115	100	8
Integrated value mapping (Overall reliability analysis)	0.826	0.46.49	100	40

not violated for any components with Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient values ranging from 0.649 to 0.976 with an integrated value mapping of 0.826. When the Cronbach alpha values of the final instrument were compared with that of the pre-test instrument, a significant decrease was observed among the student responses justified with relatively low Cronbach Alpha Coefficient values. The overall reliability analysis of the instrument (IVM) was 0.826. Generally, when the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient value is above 0.5 especially in a context where the test items to some extent are directly related to one another as it was the case in the context of this study, the instrument is considered valid and reliable for analysis. The variance which was very close to zero already implied that teachers responses to psychological contract did not significantly differ by their demographic information. To test the hypotheses of the study, the Pearson test was used because the data for the variables were normally distributed based on the statistics of the test of normality assumption trend of the data. The testing for normality assumption of every data is very important in order to avoid committing the type 1 or 2 hypothesis errors thereby, using the right test. Finally, findings were presented using frequency distribution tables and on charts with all inferential statistics presented at 95% level of confidence interval with alpha set at 0.05 levels, accepting 5% margin of error.

FINDINGS

Based on respondents' opinion on organizational citizenship behaviour, findings showed that a majority of respondents 91.0% (91.) accepted that they do voluntary activities and team work in their school. 82.0% (82.0) of respondents accepted that they willingly do what is not expected of them and more work without complaining while 8.0% (8) are not. A majority of respondents 96.0% (96) also indicated that they are able to deal with unexpected situations and do not demonstrate negative behaviours when it happens. Increase workload when a colleague is sick without complaining while 4.0% (4) were against as seen on Table 3 below.

Statistically, findings showed that transactional psychological contract has a significant and positive effect on the Organizational citizenship Behaviour (R- value 0.153*, p-value 0.130 > 0.05). The positive sign of coefficient value implies that Organizational citizenship Behaviour is more likely to be high when teachers are fair to each other in school. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated transactional psychological contract has no significant effect on organizational citizenship behaviour was rejected while the alternative hypothesis that states transactional psychological contract has significant effect on organizational citizenship behaviour was accepted.

Statistically, findings showed that relational psychological contract has a significant and positive effect on Organizational citizenship Behaviour (R- value 0.230*, p-value 0.021 > 0.05). The positive sign of coefficient value implies that teachers are more likely to have good Organizational citizenship Behaviour when there is organization trust in school. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated that relational psychological contract has no significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour was rejected while the alternative hypothesis that states relational psychological contract has a significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour was accepted. Descriptively, 86.5% of respondents indicated that they always experience a high level of relational psychological contract while 13.5% of them do not.

Statistically, findings showed that balanced psychological contract has a significant positive effect on Organizational citizenship behavior (R- value 0.095**, p-value 0.345 > 0.05). The positive sign of coefficient value implies that teachers will likely have a good organizational behavior when they experience balanced psychological contract. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated that balanced psychological contract has no significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour in primary schools in Fako Division was rejected while the alternative hypothesis that states balanced psychological contract has significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour in primary schools in Fako Division was accepted. Descriptively, 91.3 % of respondents indicated that they have balanced psychological contract while 8.7% of them denied. Table 4

Table 3. Teacher opinion on organisational citizenship behaviour

Items	Stretched				Collapsed	
	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	SA/A	D/SD
We do voluntary activities and team work in our school	46 (46.0%)	45 (45.0%)	7 (7.0%)	2 (2.2%)	91 (91.0%)	9 (9.0%)
I willingly do what is not expected of me and more works without complaining.	33 (33.0%)	59 (59.0%)	7 (7.0%)	1 (1.0%)	82 (82.0%)	8 (8.0%)
I am able to deal with unexpected situations and do not demonstrate negative behaviours when it happens. Increase workload when a colleague is sick without complaining.	46 (46.0%)	50 (50.0%)	3 (3.0%)	1 (1.0%)	96 (96.0%)	4 (4.0%)
I am good at keeping the school's image, do what is right even when the boss is not around.	42 (42.0%)	56 (56.0%)	2 (2.0%)	00 (0.0%)	98 (98.0%)	2 (2.0%)
Give advance notice if unable to come to work.	51 (51.0%)	47 (47.0%)	2 (2.0%)	00 (0.0%)	98 (98.0%)	2 (2.0%)
We usually do contributions in times of need, loss, joy, for our fellow colleagues.	60 (60.0%)	35 (35.0%)	4 (4.0%)	1 (1.0%)	95 (95.0%)	5 (5.0%)
I usually offer help to other teachers to accomplish their work	57 (57.0%)	42 (42.0%)	1 (1.0%)	00 (0.0%)	99 (99.0%)	1 (1.0%)
I voluntarily do what is not expected of me for the growth of the school.	46 (46.0%)	51 (51.0%)	3 (3.0%)	00 (0.0%)	97 (97.0%)	3 (3.0%)
Multiple Response Set (MRS)	381 (47.6%)	385 (48.1%)	29 (3.6%)	5 (0.6%)	708 (88.5%)	92 (11.5%)

*Items with coding reversed during calculation of MRS

Table 4. Summary of Findings

Questions	Statistical test	Findings
One: What is the influence of transactional psychological contract on Organisational Citizenship Behaviours in primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon?	Pearson test	Statistically, findings showed that transactional psychological contract has a significant and positive effect on the Organizational citizenship Behaviour (R-value 0.153*, p-value 0.130>0.05). The positive sign of coefficient value implies that Organizational citizenship Behaviour are more likely to be high when teachers are fair to each other in school. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated transactional psychological contract has no significant effect on organizational citizenship behaviour was rejected while the alternative hypothesis that states transactional psychological contract has significant effect on organizational citizenship behaviour was accepted.
Two: To what extent does relational psychological contract affects organizational citizenship behavior in primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon?	Pearson test	Statistically, findings showed that relational psychological contract has a significant and positive effect on Organizational citizenship Behaviour (R-value 0.230*, p-value 0.021>0.05). The positive sign of coefficient value implies that teachers are more likely to have good Organizational citizenship Behaviour when there is organization trust in school. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated that relational psychological contract has no significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour was rejected while the alternative hypothesis that states relational psychological contract has a significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour was accepted. Descriptively, 86.5% of respondents indicated that they always experience high level of relational psychological contract while 13.5% of them donot.

Table 4. Continue

Three: To what extent does balanced psychological contract affects organizational citizenship behavior in schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon.?	Pearson test	Statistically, findings showed that balanced psychological contract has a significant positive effect on Organizational citizenship behavior (R- value 0.095**, p-value 0.345>0.05). The positive sign of coefficient value implies that teachers will likely have a good organizational behavior when they experience balanced psychological contract. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated that balanced psychological contract has no significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour in primary schools in Fako Division was rejected while the alternative hypothesis that states balanced psychological contract has significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour in primary schools in Fako Division was accepted. Descriptively, 91.3 % of respondents indicated that they have balanced psychological contract while 8.7% of them denied.
---	--------------	--

DISCUSSIONS

Findings showed that transactional psychological contract has a significant and positive effect on the Organizational citizenship Behaviour. Thus, transactional psychological contract has an influence on organizational citizenship behaviour in primary schools in Fako Division. This is in line with the study carried out by Richard Todd Oppenheim (2018). Results from multiple regression suggested that each psychological contract type contributed to the variability in OCB. In addition, employer and employee fulfillment of psychological contract terms contributed to the variability in OCB, with employee fulfillment items serving as a better predictor of OCB. Employee satisfaction with work arrangement did not contribute to the variability in OCB. This study is related to the social exchange theory. This aspect of the exchange theory is that people expect equity in exchange. People expect to be rewarded equally for incurring the same costs, and when they aren't, they are displeased. Head teachers are expected to reward their teachers according to their work done. Any extra work should have an extra pay. This will go a long way to increase their organizational citizenship behaviours.

Findings showed that relational psychological contract has a significant and positive effect on Organizational citizenship Behaviour. Thus, relational psychological contract has an influence on organizational citizenship behaviour in primary schools in Fako Division. This is in line with the work of Okpu et al (2021) who using Spearman Correlation Coefficient to analyse the data, the following results were obtained: there exist a significant positive relationship between relational psychological contract and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (altruism, conscientiousness and sportsmanship). Employees are loyal and committed to their banks and they go the extra mile to ensure they meet up with obligations and duties. Managers are advised to put in place training and development initiatives and be transparent in dealing with employees to broker sustained competitive advantage. This study is related to Adam's Equity Theory as it tells us that the higher the

perception of justice and fairness an individual has, the more motivated they will be. This means that it considers an outcome or distribution that favors it to be fair and does not consider its advantageous pay to be relatively unfair compared to similar others. If many employees feel that their compensation is not fair or equitable, their commitment to the diversity and inclusion of the organization is likely to diminish significantly. In particular, the introduction of fair procedures accompanied by fair results leads to a significant increase in employee engagement in an environment of low trust. When leaders of organizations express a desire to address inequality, set clear goals for fairness, and then take action, they signal a commitment that will underpin their diversity and inclusion efforts (Mansour, 2021). Head teachers are expected to relate with their teachers, giving them equal treatment, exhibit a certain level of trust, loyalty so they can get that in return, and thus organisational behaviour of teachers.

Findings showed that balanced psychological contract has a significant positive effect on Organizational citizenship behaviour. This is in line with the empirical work of Retnol et al (2021) The result of this study is that there is a significant influence between the relational contract and balance contract on organizational citizenship behaviour. It is also related to the Adams Equity Theory which is the balance between the effort an employee puts into their work (input), and the result they get in return (output). Input includes hard work, skills, and enthusiasm. Output can be things like salary, recognition, and responsibility. A proper balance between input and output ensures that an employee feels satisfied and motivated, contributing to their productivity. There should be a balance between the transactional and relational psychological contracts. This increases the organisational citizenship behaviour of teachers in primary schools in Fako division, South West region of Cameroon.

CONCLUSION

Generally, it can be concluded psychological contracts:

transactional, relational, balanced has an influence on the organisational behaviour of teachers in primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon. In most primary schools, head teachers who practice or exhibit these behaviours tend to have high productivity in schools. Their teachers show a certain level of commitment to the school. It is recommended of head teachers and employees to always relate with their teachers transactionally, relationally, and there should always be a balance between the two. As a result of this, it can be observed that organizational citizenship behavior can be well described through psychological contract. The purpose of this research was to show that the informal or unwritten contracts such as the transactional, relational and balanced are useful and valid in teaching and administration and also affects organizational citizenship behaviors of teachers in Primary schools in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon.

REFERENCES

- Adams JS (1965). *Inequity in social exchange*. In L. Berkowitz (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (pp. 267-299). Academic Press.
- Argyris C (1960). *Understanding organizational behavior*. Dorsey.
- Argyris C (1960). *Understanding organizational behaviour*. Tavistock Publications.
- Bellou V (2007). *Achieving long-term customer satisfaction through organizational culture: Evidence from the health care sector*. *Managing Service Quality*, 17(5), 510-22.
- Bhawna C (2019). *Psychological Contract and Organizational Citizenship behaviour: Exploring the interrelatedness through cross validation*. *Acad. Strat. Manag. J.* www.researchgate.net
- Blau P (2009). *Exchange and power in social life*. Transaction Publishers. www.taylorfrancis.com
- Contract of Employees and Employer. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 89, 52 – 72.
- Mansour T (2021). *Fairness & Equality - An Organization Dilemma*
- Okpu et al (2021). *Relational psychological contract and Organisational citizenship behaviour of Commercial Banks in Bayelsa State*. *Int. J. Bus. Manag. Invention (IJBMI)*. www.ijbmi.com
- Organ DW (1988). A Restatement of the Satisfaction-Performance Hypothesis. *J. Manag.* 14(4), 547-57.
- Organ DW (1997). Organizational citizenship behavior: It's construct cleanup time. *Human Performance*, 10(2), 85-97.
- Retno et al (2021). The Effect of Psychological Contracts: Transactional, Relational, Balance on Organizational Citizenship Behaviors University Staff 150 in Indonesia and Malaysia. *Int. J. Sci. Res. Manag. (IJSRM)*, Volume 09 Issue02PagesSH-2021-550-554.
- Richard T (2018). *The impact of Psychological contract on Organisational citizenship behaviour*. <https://scholarworks.calstate.edu>
- Robinson L, Morrison E (1995). Psychological contracts and OCB: The effect of unfulfilled obligations. *J. Organizational Behavior*, 16, 289.
- Rousseau DM, Guillermo ED (2001). Mutuality and Reciprocity in the Psychological
- Sonnenberg M, Koene B, Paauwe J (2011). Balancing HRM: the psychological contract of employees: A multi-level study. *Personnel Review*, 40(6), 664-683.
- Yin J, Lin X, Cong W (2008). The empirical research of the relationships between psychological contract types and organizational outcomes. *Wireless Communications, Networking and Mobile Computing*, doi:10.1109/WiCom.2008.1694.